

APPLICATION OF PRECERAMIC POLYMER FOR SHAPE FORMING OF MULTIPHASE SiC/Si₃N₄ CERAMIC PARTS

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SUMMARY: The purpose of the present work is to fabricate shape-complex SiC/Si₃N₄ multiphase ceramic parts (such as blade) using preceramic polymer (Polycarbosilane PCS) as shape-forming binders. SiC/Si₃N₄ multiphase ceramics are formed by in-situ pyrolysis and sintering from PCS/Si₃N₄ green body. Divinylbenzene(DVB) is used as active diluent agent to prepare slurry of PCS/DVB/Si₃N₄ at room temperature, and as cross-linking agent to make solid green body of PCS/DVB/Si₃N₄. It is necessary to control precisely rate of pyrolysis temperature of 250-450 °C under 0.3 °C/min in order to obtain a pyrolysis with body of deformation-free and crack-free. Before sintering, decreasing the carbon-rich content in the pyrolysis body, the density of sintered body can be enhanced.

KEYWORDS: precursor, SiC/Si₃N₄ ceramic, shaping, pyrolysis, sintering

INTRODUCTION

SiC/Si₃N₄ multiphase ceramic is one of the most promising candidate materials for high temperature structural components in heat engines for its attractive characteristics such as low density and excellent resistance to corrosion, wear, oxidation and heat-shocking at high temperature. Once it was used in heat engine, fuel would be saved, the working temperature, efficiency and power of the engine would be elevated. It may be the bottle-neck to prepare such engine parts as turbine blade and rotor to realize the practicability of a ceramic engine. The shaping technologies in common use in nowadays (e.g. injection and casting) are not much promising because of their shortcomings as high cost, long cycle, poor property of product and so on. The authors of this paper prepared ceramic blades using organosilicon precursor as shaping binder, and discussed the effects of processing parameters on the structure and performance of the pyrolyzed and sintered blades.

Preceramic polymer such as polycarbosilane (PCS) can be used as binder to fabricate ceramic part [1-5]. Unlike conventional binders (PE,PP etc.) that are totally burned out, during pyrolysis, the preceramic polymer binder can be chemically transformed into a continuous ceramic phase. For example, while PCS is used as a binder of Si₃N₄ powder, PCS can be changed into nanophase SiC at over 1000 °C, and a multiphase ceramic can be in-situ formed in the final part.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Polycarbosilane (PCS), as a preceramic polymer (dark black brittle melt point 125-135 °C) was dissolved into divinylbenzene (DVB) which acted as active dilute agent, to form viscous liquid for binder solution at room temperature. α - Si_3N_4 powder and Sintering aids ($\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3$) were incorporated into PCS/DVB solution by ultrasonic dispersion to form a slurry of PCS/DVB/ $\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3$, then the slurry was cast into a mold. Heat treatment for curing of slurry was 130 °C, 7 hours at 1.6 MPa nitrogen pressure for preventing DVB from evaporation. First, Green body of ceramic parts was pyrolysed in nitrogen flow at 0.3~1 C/min from room temperature to 1000 °C, held for 1 hour at 1000 °C; Then, the pyrolysed body was cooled to room temperature in the furnace. Second, the pyrolyzed body was heated in nitrogen flow at 20 °C/min from room temperature to 1600 °C, held 1 hour at 1600 °C to crystalline amorphous SiC, and to react Si_3N_4 with free carbon derived from pyrolysed PCS, and then sintered at 10 C/min from 1600 °C to 1930 °C, held for 120 minutes at 1930 °C and 1.0 MPa nitrogen pressure.

Density of specimens was determined by Archimedes immersion technique. Phase identification of sintered body was performed by X-ray diffraction using CuK α -radiation. Microstructure of pyrolysed body and sintered body was examined by scan electron microscopy (SEM). Fracture strength was evaluated using three-point bending over a 20 mm span. The ratio span to height specimens is 5.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Preparation of Slurry and Preforms

The slurry was composed of Si_3N_4 powder, PCS, DVB, sintering aids and shaping aids (crosslinking initiator and coupling agent). The role of DVB in the slurry was: 1) a diluent to reduce the viscosity of the slurry, and 2) a solidifying agent to react with Si-H bonds in PCS (initiated by dicumylphene, pop above 120 °C) and self-crosslink due to the vinyl groups in its molecular. The effects of the concentration of DVB on the property of the crosslinked preform were listed in Table 1. According to these results, the ratio of PCS to DVB should be 1.5:1. Other experimental data proved that middle-molecular-weight PCS was appropriate and coupling agent (e.g. titanate serials) should added into the slurry before ball milling to improve the disconcentration of ceramic particles in precursor solution. For the same aim, further dispersing treatment by means of super sonic should be adopted.

Table 1: Effects of PCS/DVB ratio on the facade of pyrolysed parts

PCS/DVB	2:1	1.5:1	1:1
outward appearance of pyrolysed parts	metamorphosed obviously	without distortion no visible defects	cracked evidently

Different compositions of binder solution were used to prepare crosslinked preform and the crosslinking degrees of each sample were compared in Table 2. The data showed that middlemolecular-weight PCS was seemly and the incorporation of about 2wt.% of pop as initiator would promote the crosslinking reaction. IR analysis of the slurry, the crosslinked preform and the precursor saluted in xylene after extracting the preform revealed that most of

Si-H bonds did not crosslink as we expected. So, the microstructure of the crosslinked product was cured DVB net with PCS chains running through it.

Table 2: Crosslinking degrees of preforms with different binder compositions

	1	2	3	4	5
LPCS	100		100		
MPCS		100		100	
DVB	50	50	50	50	100
DCP		3		3	2
Crosslinking degree (%)	31.4	42.4	42.6	60.8	97

NOTE: All preforms were cured at 180 C in 1.0-2.0MPa N₂ for 8h. The crosslinking degrees were determined by measuring the maintained masses of the preforms after immersing them into xylene at room temperature for 24hrs and then drying them at 80 C in vacuum for 2hrs. MPCS=middle molecular weight PCS, LPCS=low molecular weight PCS

As discussed above, DCP was effective to initiate the self-polymerization of DVB and partial crosslinking of Si-H with vinyl group. TG analysis showed that DCP began decomposition at about 120 °C. Besides, the boiling point of DVB is 138 °C. So, the crosslinking reaction should be performed at 120-138 °C and nitrogen pressure (1.0-2.0 MPa) should be adopted to avoid the volatilisation of DVB and the oxidation of PCS.

Pyrolyzation of the Preforms

TG analysis (10 °C/min, Ar) of shaped preforms revealed that most of the loss occurred below 550 °C, especially from 250 °C to 550 °C (see Figure 1). The said weight loss was due to the volatilisation of low-molecular-weight oligomer and pyrolyzation of the crosslinked precursor. it was important to control the heating rate this temperature scale to reduce the amount of the volatiled and pyrolysed gas and the possibility of deforming, cracking and bulging. Heating rates of 0.3, 0.5 and 1.0 °C/min were introduced to optimize the heating rate. Results in Table 3 showed that defect-free pyrolyzed parts could be obtained at a heating rate lower than 0.3°C/min.

Fig 1: TG curves of crosslinked samples

Note: 1: DVB/DCP 2: LPCS/DVB/DCP 3: MPCS/DVB/DCP. 4. LPCS/DVB/DCP/Si₃N₄

Table 3: The property of ceramic parts pyrolysed at different heating rates

heating rate (°C/min)	property of pyrolyzed parts
1	heavily distorted and cracked
0.5	slightly distorted, cracked at large cross section
0.3	no deformation, crack-free

TG curves in Figure 1 also showed that the weight loss above 800 °C was negligible. This result implied that the inorganization of the precursor was almost complete before 800 °C. The pyrolyzed ceramic bars that were further treated up to 1500 °C (holding for 120 min) showed very slight shrinkage and weight loss (about 2 wt.%). Their bending strength (60 ± 10 MPa) were almost the same as that before the treatment. So it was necessary to elevate the sintering temperature to improve the strength of the parts.

As concluded above, the microstructure of the cured preceramic binder was a inter-joined 3dimensioned network with PCS chains running through crosslinked DVB moleculars, and in the network there was about 12-18 wt.% of uncured PCS that would melt at elevated temperature to cause distortion of the preform. This kind of deformation could be reduced by extracting 8-10 wt.% of the soluble PCS out of the preform with xylene as solvent, without distorting the preform during extraction. The extracted preforms were heated at a faster temperature rate, and defect-free pyrolyzed parts were obtained with highly reduced linear shrinkage. The reasons for such a improvement might be that absence of low molecular weight PCS decreased the volatilization during pyrolyzation and gangways for pyrolyzed gas were left after extraction.

Sintering of Pyrolyzed Parts

Pyrolysed body has too low density, much more porosity and poor strength to use. It is desired to sinter for dense SiC/Si₃N₄ ceramic parts. In the sintering process, free carbon derived from pyrolysis of PCS/DVB will react with sintering aids (Al₂O₃, Y₂O₃, La₂O₃, etc.) to decrease the amount of liquid phase for sintering, and react with SiO₂ on the surface of Si₃N₄ powder to increase the content of SiC. Those are retarded to densely sinter. Thus decarbonation is important prior to sintering.

Table 4: Weight loss and density of Sintered body by deferent pretreatment

specimen	pretreatment	density of pyrolysis body (g/cm ³)	weight loss of sintering (%)	density of sintered body (g/cm ³)	relative density (%)	defect
pyrolysis body		2.25	21.1	3.236	92.2	no
extraction and pyrolysis body		1.79	13.5	3.274	93.6	no
pyrolysis body	oxidation	2.20	15.7	3.351	95.8	deform and crack
pyrolysis body	NH ₃	2.18	19.5	3.328	93.6	no
extraction and pyrolysis body	NH ₃	1.70	11.4	3.371	96.4	no

Table 4 shows weight loss and density of Sintered body by different pretreatment before sintering. The result indicates that deformation and crack had been found in the sintered specimen which the removal of carbon-rich by oxidating was at 700 °C for 120 minutes, but no defect had been found in the sintered specimens when oxidation condition changed to 500 °C for 180 minutes. That is because oxygen reacts not only with carbon-rich, but also with amorphous SiC derived from PCS. Large amount of SiO₂ formed on the surface of pore, in the sintering process, liquid-phase sintering aid was so heterogeneous distributing that nonhomogeneously shrinkage of sintering resulted deformation and crack. Otherwise, gradual change of carbon-rich content from the surface to the middle will influence the well distributed of composition and microstructure of sintering body. The improvement of relative density for sintered body which had been treated with NH₃ is not pronounced due to low efficient of removal of carbon-rich. Density of sintered body which had been treated by extraction of PCS and removal of carbon-rich in NH₃ atmosphere is high due to low content of SiC, carbon-rich derived from PCS/DVB. Thus the main factors which influenced densely sintering are the content of PCS/DVB in the green body, SiC and carbon-rich in as-fired body

Effect of sintering temperature on density of the sintered body is shown as Table 5. Increasing sintering temperature, density of sintered body can be enhanced. Increasing size of blade, density of sintered body decreased. A multiphase SiC/Si₃N₄ dense ceramic part, with a relative density of 93 % and no defect (such as deform, crack etc.), is obtained at 1930 °C for 120 minute.

Table 5: Effect of sintering temperature on the density of sintered body

	1850 °C/120 min.		1870 °C/120 min.		1900 °C/120 min.	
	desity (g/cm ³)	relative density (%)	density (g/cm ³)	relative density (%)	density (g/cm ³)	relative density (%)
large blade	2.87	82	3.02	86	3.15	90
small blade	3.18	91	3.27	93.5	3.31	94.7

Microstructure and Strength of Sintered Body

Figure 2 shows X-ray diffraction patterns of sintered specimen of PCS/DVB/Si₃N₄. This result indicates that β-SiC and β-Si₃N₄ grain phase was in-situ formed in the final sample. β-SiC come from crystallization of amorphous silicon carbide derived from PCS. β-Si₃N₄ come from transformation of α-Si₃N₄.

Fig. 3: Microstructure of the etched and fracture surface of sintered parts

The etched and fracture surface of $\text{SiC}/\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4$ multiphase ceramic is shown as Figure 3. The fracture mode is predominantly intergranular debonding. $\beta\text{-Si}_3\text{N}_4$ grain shape is pillar-like. $\beta\text{-SiC}$ is agglomerated submicron particle. Mechanical property of sintered body (Table 6) is not high. The research on the improvement of mechanical property is under process.

Table 6: Mechanical property of $\text{SiC}/\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4$ multiphase ceramic derived from PCS/DVB/ Si_3N_4

density (g/cm^3)	relative density (%)	σ_b (R.T.) (MPa)	K_{IC} ($\text{MPa} \cdot \text{m}^{1/2}$)
3.20	91	403	7.530

CONCLUSIONS

1. Low viscosity slurry could be obtained using MPCs as precursor, DVB as diluent and crosslinking agent and titanate as coupling agent.
2. The crosslinking reaction of PCS/DVB/DCP was performed at about 120°C in N_2 (1.0-2.0MPa) for 8 hours.
3. Defect-free pyrolyzed parts could be prepared as heating rate was lower than $0.3^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$; it was effective to improve the property of pyrolyzed parts by extracting low molecular weight PCS out of the green body prior to pyrolyzation.
4. Extraction before pyrolyzation and using NH_3 as sintering atmosphere would decrease the content of free carbon in sintering product, and this would increase the density of the sintered parts.

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